

Economic of structural changes in economic sectors

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Abstract: The Gross Domestic Product (GDP) in Uzbekistan expanded 6.40 percent in the second quarter of 2024 over the same quarter of the previous year. GDP Annual Growth Rate in Uzbekistan is expected to be 6.20 percent by the end of this quarter, according to Trading Economics global macro models and analysts expectations. In this article, the comparison of various models related to macroeconomic balance and economic growth is studied on the basis of various graphs, formulas and tables, and their comparisons are made. In addition, the specific characteristics of the models and their application in what period and for what economic systems are covered in detail. Economic growth refers to an increase in the size of a country's economy over a period of time. The size of an economy is typically measured by the total production of goods and services in the economy, which is called gross domestic product (GDP).

Key words: economic growth, capital, labor, goods market (IS), money market (LM), balance of payments (BP), interest rate, return on capital, technologies, capital accumulation, accumulation level.

Enter. It is known from the history of economy that from the beginning of the natural economy to the period of the current market economy, the economic views specific

to each economic process were created during that period, and in many cases these economic ideas. Although the structure of economic management changed for that period, they also lost their power and paved the way for the formation of other economic ideas. Similarly, along with general economic ideas, specific economic ideas, for example, the ideas of scientists focused on economic growth, are different in different periods, and the factors included in them are also significantly different from each other.

In this article, the definition of economic growth according to different researchers, answers to the main questions related to the sources of economic growth, the analysis of various models related to economic growth and their components, as well as the reasons for the differences in economic activity across countries. It will be possible to get acquainted with wide and comprehensive information. Questions on this topic are important not only for economic theories, but also for macroeconomic analysis and social science. This article examines the features and differences between the economic and general equilibrium models, the Harrod-Domar model, the Robert Solow economic growth model, the IS-LM-BP model, and the AD-AS model. In addition, the ideas of economic growth of D. Acemoglu, one of the modern economic scientists, are analyzed.

Literature analysis. Many scientists have conducted research on the theory of economic growth. But in this article, we will get acquainted with the most comprehensive and popular theories of economic growth and equilibrium. First of all, according to the scientists of our country, including Dzhumaev, economic growth means a long-term increase in the level of potential production corresponding to the conditions of full employment. According to this scientist,

economic growth means an increase in aggregate supply, or in other words, an increase in real and potential GDP [1].

Let's talk about the Harrod-Domar growth model. This model is the result of independent research of British economist Roy Harrod and American economist Evsey Domer. According to this model, economic growth depends on three factors: capital (K), labor (L), resources (R). $Y = F(K, L, R)$ where R and L are capital production are considered factors that lead to inflation [2]. Now we turn our attention to the Solow-Swan model named after the economists Robert Solow and Trevor Swan, or the Solow model in many literatures. These scientists introduced the Solow model in 1956 with the publication of an extensive paper [3].

Bob Solow later developed the future prospects of this model and its applications, and was awarded the Nobel Prize for this contribution to economics. This model changed not only our view of economic growth, but also our approach to all areas of macroeconomics. Professor Xavier Sala-i-Martin in his work entitled "Economic Growth" listed three different factors as the factors that ensure economic growth. They are capital $K(t)$, labor $L(t)$ and intelligence $T(t)$ [4].

In this case, the production function is as follows: $Y(t) = F[K(t), L(t), T(t)]$ Here $Y(t)$ represents the amount of production during a certain period. The difference between this economic model and the Harrod-Domar model lies in the last factor. According to him, it was mentioned that resources cannot be used without technology and knowledge in society, and it is intelligence and technology that make resources stronger. emphasized. In his opinion, this model is suitable for countries with "high population density, capital shortage, and limited natural resources" [5]. Such countries include countries like India, Pakistan, and Egypt. Professor

Acemoglu's main contribution to development economics was his work on the primacy of political institutions in development, a theory he developed in *Why Nations Decline*. In this, he emphasizes that there are two main types of institutions: extractive and inclusive. Extractive institutions were created to serve a small or single individual (for example, nobles during the feudal system). But inclusive institutions are managed by the majority and therefore intend to improve the general well-being of the population [6]. The Ramsey model is a neoclassical model of economic growth. It describes the time evolution of capital and consumption in a closed economy with exponential population growth. In this work, the Ramsey model for the total time evolution of the population is formulated. Also, Ramsey's rule in economics is the "rule of inverse elasticity". In it, the amount of tax imposed on products should be opposite to the elasticity of demand for products [7]. Research methodology. The article includes a systematic approach, statistics, comparison, scientific abstraction, and existing domestic and foreign literature related to economic growth and Theories of economic growth are compared and graphically illustrated by studying the articles.

Methodology. Systematic analysis, statistical-economic and scientific abstraction, comparative and structural analysis and a number of other methods were used in the article.

Results and analysis.

According to the preliminary data of the State Statistics Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan, in the first half of 2020, economic growth rates were maintained, albeit small. The volume of the gross domestic product (GDP) was 255.3 trillion soums, and the growth rate was 0.2%. Compared to the same period

last year, this indicator was 6%. The growth of gross added value in industries was 0.3%. ADB's "Asian Development Prospects" (ADO) annual economic publication CPI may stay in the 8.0-8.5% YoY territory until May 2024, after which, if the government proceeds with the spike in the tariffs, inflation may pick up again. In this environment, the NBU's key rate of 14.0% may well have to be kept unchanged until the beginning of 2025, when the dust from the higher services inflation settles. CPI may stay in the 8.0-8.5% YoY territory until May 2024, after which, if the government proceeds with the spike in the tariffs, inflation may pick up again. In this environment, the NBU's key rate of 14.0% may well have to be kept unchanged until the beginning of 2025, when the dust from the higher services inflation settles.

Figure 1.

CPI may stay in the 8.0-8.5% YoY territory until May 2024, after which, if the government proceeds with the spike in the tariffs, inflation may pick up again. In this environment, the NBU's key rate of 14.0% may well have to be kept unchanged until the beginning of 2025, when the dust from the higher services inflation settles. Given the growing economy, the total number of people employed rose from 8.5 million in 1995 to 13.5 million in 2011.[28] This increase of nearly 25% in the labor force lagged behind the increase in GDP during the same period (64%, see chart), which implied a significant increase in labor productivity. Official unemployment is low: less than 30,000 job seekers were registered in government labor exchanges in 2005-2006 (0.3% of the labor force).[28] Underemployment, on the other hand, is quite high, especially in agriculture, which accounts for fully 28% of all employed, many working part-time on small household plots.

Source: Stat.uz, 1st quarter of 2023

Budget policy is growth-supportive as, after consolidating from 5.5% to 4.0% of GDP in 2022, the consolidated budget deficit (comprising of state budget, sovereign fund, and budget SOEs) widened again to 4.9% of GDP on a 4Q rolling basis as of mid-2023. In July, the monthly CPI stood at -0.2% -a slight increase compared to the previous month (-0.3%) (Figure 1). In the corresponding period of 2022, the monthly inflation rate was slightly higher at -0.1%. Compared to the beginning of the year, the general price index increased by 3.3%, which represents a significant slowdown compared to the corresponding period of 2022 (6.4%). The average monthly inflation over the first seven months of 2023 was 0.7%.

The Gross Domestic Product (GDP) in Uzbekistan was worth 90.89 billion US dollars in 2023, according to official data from the World Bank. The GDP value of Uzbekistan represents 0.09 percent of the world economy.

The gross domestic product (GDP) measures of national income and output for a given country's economy. The gross domestic product (GDP) is equal to the total expenditures for all final goods and services produced within the country in a stipulated period of time.

Source: https://stat.uz/images/uploads/reliz-2023/narx_-2023_-yanvar-iyul-5.pdf

Domestic demand appears well supported by credit expansion, with retail lending up 40% YoY in real terms, continued remittances inflow and other spillover effects of the Russia-Ukraine conflict, continued export growth, and – most recently – by the fiscal side, as contrary to our initial expectations the consolidated budget

deficit widened by almost 1ppt of GDP over the course of 1H23.

Summary

To conclude from the above, structural reform and development of the economy requires the introduction of a modern and inclusive institutional system based on rapid identification and elimination of existing problems and obstacles.

Including:

- ensuring consistency between macroeconomic stability, economic growth goals and structural reforms;
- introduction of effective systems and mechanisms based on modern forecasting models for managing economic cycles caused by external and internal factors;
- the absence of a comprehensive system and coordinating state body, regulatory framework, criteria and evaluation methodology for the development and implementation of measures aimed at reducing poverty,
- due to the fact that the tasks of social support and involvement in entrepreneurship are not clearly separated, the effectiveness of the work carried out with the relevant population groups is low;
- lack of a clear approach and principles for socio-economic development of the regions;
- without ensuring interdependence between the regional and sectoral development of the economy and rational use of the existing potential and "relative advantage" criteria in the development of regions;
- taking into account human capital and demographic factors in the deployment of production forces;
- determining specific approaches to the development of small and medium-sized

businesses in the country, systematizing financial and non-financial support for entrepreneurship;

- elimination of shortcomings in the evaluation of the effectiveness of the funds allocated from the programs;

- to increase labor productivity in the areas considered as the fundamental drivers of the country's industrial development;

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